

Figure S1. The phylogeny of Anglerfishes I. Inset of ASTRAL-III species tree showing relationships of the outgroups (*Antigonia capros* and *Tetraodontoidei*), *Lophiidae*, and *Chaunacidae*. Dots at branches indicate coalescent supports (CS) of less than 1.0. Terminal branches leading to tips have no lengths, but all other branches are scaled to coalescent units. Illustrations by Julie Johnson.

Figure S2. The phylogeny of Anglerfishes II. Inset of ASTRAL-III species tree showing relationships of half of *Ceratioidea*. Dots at branches indicate coalescent supports (CS) of less than 1.0. Terminal branches leading to tips have no lengths, but all other branches are scaled to coalescent units. Illustrations by Julie Johnson.

Figure S3. The phylogeny of Anglerfishes III. Inset of ASTRAL-III species tree showing relationships of half of *Ogcocephalidae* and *Antennariidae*. Dots at branches indicate coalescent supports (CS) of less than 1.0. Terminal branches leading to tips have no lengths, but all other branches are scaled to coalescent units. Illustrations by Julie Johnson.

Figure S4. Concordance and discordance in anglerfish phylogeny. Scatterplots showing relationships between (a) ultrafast bootstraps and branch lengths, (b) gene concordance factors and branch lengths, (c) site concordance factors and gene concordance factors, and (d) site concordance factors and branch lengths. Key nodes are numbered on the tree to the left, and dotted lines on the phylogeny indicate anomaly zones.

Figure S5. The anomaly zone in ceratioid phylogeny. Simplified topologies resulting from (a) the ASTRAL-III species tree summary of individual gene trees generated in IQ-TREE2, (b) the maximum likelihood phylogeny generated from the analysis of partitioned UCE sets in IQ-TREE2, and (c) the analysis in IQ-TREE2 where all UCES were concatenated into a single partition. Numbers at nodes in (a) are coalescent supports and in (b-c) are ultrafast bootstrap supports. Shaded gray indicates the location of the detected anomaly zone in each phylogeny.

Figure S6. Chaunacid diversity. Maximum likelihood tree of the mitochondrial locus *COI* showing relationships between species in *Chaunacidae*. Red dot indicates the crown node for *Chaunax*. (b) Heatmap showing uncorrected genetic dissimilarity values between species in *Chaunacidae*. Note the poor resolution within *Chaunax*. Illustration by Julie Johnson.

Figure S7. Convergent Degeneration of Adaptive Immunity in Anglerfishes. Simplified phylogeny with ancestral state reconstructions of different components of the vertebrate adaptive immune system using stochastic character mapping (R phytools) on a simplified version of the anglerfish timetree presented in Figure 1.

Figure S8. Evolution of Sexual Dimorphism in Anglerfishes. Time tree with ancestral state reconstructions of sexual dimorphism in anglerfishes (treated as a three-state character) using stochastic character mapping (R phytools) on a reduced version of the anglerfish timetree presented in Figure 1.